

READING DIFFICULTIES OF LEARNERS IN THE POST PANDEMIC AS PERCEIVED BY TEACHERS IN A PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOL IN BUENAVISTA, QUEZON

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 32

Issue 1

Pages: 99-105

Document ID: 2025PEMJ3045

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14850834

Manuscript Accepted: 01-05-2025

Reading Difficulties of Learners in the Post Pandemic as Perceived by Teachers in a Public Elementary School in Buenavista, Quezon

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Abstract

This study aimed to identify the factors contributing to reading difficulties among learners in the post-pandemic as perceived by teachers in a public elementary school in Buenavista, Quezon, for the SY 2023-2024. Using a descriptive research method, the researcher selected 60 teachers from Buenavista Elementary School through random sampling. Data were collected via a questionnaire focusing on phonological awareness, auditory processing, visual memory, and comprehension of the language. The findings revealed significant challenges across all four areas. In terms of phonological awareness, children struggled the most with recognizing and producing rhyming words, blending and segmenting single-syllable spoken words, and forming words into different sounds, with mean agreement scores of 4.45, 4.3, and 4.2, respectively. Understanding phonemes and pronouncing initial, medial vowel, and final sounds in CVC words were also challenging but to a slightly lesser degree, with mean scores of 4.1 and 4.0. Regarding auditory processing, the greatest difficulty was in remembering what was heard, with a mean score of 4.63. Explaining the meaning of spoken language due to limited vocabulary, maintaining attention, and making sense of sounds also posted significant challenges, with mean scores of 4.4 and 4.2. Following multi-step instructions was the least challenging in this area, with a mean score of 4.10. For visual memory, the highest difficulty was in recalling text, images, and details, with a mean score of 4.23. Creating mental pictures of information, understanding word sequences, and copying information from books or boards were also problematic, with mean scores of 4.22, 4.15, and 3.88, respectively. Recognizing letters or numbers was the least challenging, with a mean score of 3.82. In terms of language comprehension, children find it most difficult to follow directions, as indicated by a mean score of 4.55. Processing text details and extracting meaning from written words and sentence structures were also significant challenges, with mean scores of 4.23 and 4.2. Responding to conversations or questions in texts was the least difficult, with a mean score of 3.95. The study employed Spearman's Rho correlation to determine the significance of these factors, revealing a substantial positive correlation between phonological awareness, auditory processing, visual memory, and language comprehension. With a p-value less than 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected, indicating that these factors are significantly correlated.

Keywords: *auditory processing, comprehension of the language, difficulties, phonological awareness, post pandemic, visual memory*

Introduction

Covid-19 has had a great impact on education. Children from Kindergarten to grade three were greatly affected in terms of Reading Performance. For almost two years. No face-to-face classes were experienced by the learners. What contributed much to the poor academic performance of pupils is the reading difficulties.

What contributed much to the poor academic performance of pupils is the reading difficulties. The researcher observes that most of the pupils in a public elementary school specifically the primary level in Buenavista District find difficulties in reading. Probably because of the absence of face-to-face classes for almost two years. Some pupils cannot read stories, paragraphs, sentences and even words fluently. They are suffering difficulties when it comes to reading. Some are struggling readers even if they are in grade three.

Based on the study of Malik and Jason 2021. Covid-19 pandemic has had a profound impact on the teaching learning process of the learners.

The primary goal of this study is to determine the reading difficulties of learners in the post pandemic as perceived by teachers in Buenavista, Quezon.

Based from the authors, some of the causes of reading problems are phonological awareness, auditory processing difficulties, visual memory difficulties, and comprehension of the language (Nel, Nel & Hugo 2016: 222-227)

The researcher will determine the reading difficulties of learners in the post pandemic as perceived by teachers in a public elementary school in Buenavista, Quezon. To help pupils, improve their reading skill.

Research Questions

This study determined Reading difficulties of learners as perceived by teachers in a public elementary school in Buenavista, Quezon for the SY 2023-2024. Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What are the factors of reading difficulties of the learners in the Post Pandemic in the following areas:

- 1.1. phonological awareness;
- 1.2. auditory processing;
- 1.3. visual memory; and
- 1.4. comprehension of the language?
2. Is there any significant relationship between the perceived factors that cause reading difficulties of learners after pandemic?
3. Based on the results, what is the plan to solve the existing reading difficulties of learners?

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher used descriptive method to collect significant data in research study. Descriptive method is a type of research that is used to describe the characteristics of a population. The instrument is in the form of distributing questionnaire to gather necessary information from the respondents.

Based from Shona Mc Combes the descriptive survey methods aims accurately and systematically describe a population, situation or phenomenon. It can answer what, where, when and how questions, but not why questions.

Respondents

The researcher used purposive sampling design. The purposive sampling design is a sampling technique in which researcher relies on his or her own judgement when choosing members of population to participate in the study.

The researcher selected teachers who were teaching in Buenavista Elementary School S.Y 2023-2024 and the Reading difficulties of learners focused of the study. The respondents are 60 teachers from Buenavista Elementary School.

Instrument

The researcher used questionnaire. This questionnaire is a Likert scale of: 5 – Very much agree, 4 - Much agree, 3 - Agree, 2 – Less agree, 1- Least agree. For understanding about the Reading difficulties of learners in the post pandemic as perceived teachers in Buenavista, Quezon. The researcher prepared questionnaire to the respondents, and the Reading difficulties of learners. The questionnaire was validated by 2 experts.

Procedure

Prior to the conduct of the study, the researcher sent a letter to the school's principal and adviser. Upon approval, the researcher administered the instrument to the target respondents.

In administering the questionnaire, the researcher used the time allotted for vacant time to avoid distraction of class discussion. The teacher's response gave enough time to answer the questions. After data gathering, the researcher collected them for tallying the scores and to apply the statistical treatment to be used in the study.

The descriptive research design method using likert scale is used in order to rate the factors that cause reading difficulties of learners as perceived by teachers. Data were gathered through "purposive sampling" both male and female teachers of Buenavista Elementary School in Buenavista, Quezon were selected to fill the questionnaire. The data will be gathered through face-to-face survey following the safety health protocols to prevent the spread of the virus.

Data Analysis

In this study, the researcher used statistical measures to treat the collected data. All the data were carefully read and examined for analysis. They were tallied and entered into a master list of the data collection sheet. Percentage and Frequency is used to interpret the level of difficulty of the learners in the following areas. To test the significant relationship involving ordinal variables, the researcher used the Spearman's Rho correlation.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 illustrates the factors of reading difficulty of learners in the area of phonological awareness. Table shows the level of agreement of the respondents with the phonological awareness of the children. It reveals that children find it difficult to recognize and produce rhyming words, which are utilized to the highest agreement with the mean of 4.45. The least level of agreement in finding difficulties with phonological awareness is pronouncing the initial, medial vowel, and final sounds in CVC words with a mean of 4.0.

In a similar study conducted by Ferraz et al., (2020), One of the most important indicators of success in this field has been identified as phonological awareness (e.g., Melby-Lervåg et al., 2012). As evidenced by numerous studies (e.g., Newbury et al., 2020), phonological awareness is crucial for word recognition, reading accuracy and fluency.

The table shows respondents' assessment of reading difficulties in phonological awareness. The most challenging factor, with an average rating of 4.45, is reading new words due to undeveloped skills in breaking words into different sounds. Overall, the average

difficulty rating is 4.21, indicating that respondents very much agree (VMA) that these factors contribute significantly to reading difficulties. The least challenging factor is blending and segmenting single-syllable spoken words, with an average rating of 4.0.

Table 1. Respondents Assessment on the factors of reading difficulty of learners in the area of phonological awareness

The children find difficulties in phonological awareness which concerns in...	M	INT	R
1.recognizing and producing rhyming words	4.45	VMA	1
2.pronouncing the initial, medial vowel and final sounds in CVC words.	4.0	MA	5
3.reading new words as they have not developed the skill of breaking words into different sounds	4.2	VMA	3
4.adding and individual sounds (phonemes) in simple, one - syllable words to make new words.	4.1	MA	4
5.blending and segmenting on series of single - syllable spoken words.	4.3	VMA	2
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN	4.21		

The table 2 shows the level of agreement of the respondents with the auditory processing of the children. It reveals that children find it difficult to remember what they listened to, as indicated by the highest agreement with the mean of 4.63. The least level of agreement in finding difficulties with auditory processing is following instructions, especially with multiple steps, with a mean of 4.10.

Table 2. Respondents Assessment on the factors of reading difficulty of learners in the area of auditory processing

The children find difficulties in auditory processing which concerns in...	WM	INT	R
1.maintaining attention span in presenting lesson.	4.2	VMA	3.5
2. following instructions, especially with multiple steps.	4.10	MA	5
3.making sense of the sounds they heard.	4.22	VMA	3.5
4.remembering what they listened to.	4.63	VMA	1
5.explaining the meaning of spoken language due to lack of vocabulary.	4.4	VMA	2
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN	4.31		

A lot of students came to understand that their favorite method of learning had altered from traditional classroom settings to remote studies which mostly demanded lesser sound stimuli during this pandemic period. It is possible that this decrease in the amount of auditory information might have impaired the ability of students to process auditory information, making it difficult for them to comprehend and interpret spoken language with ease. Auditory processing deficits and flaws in auditory sequencing skills could be responsible for difficulties when discriminating between words that sound alike or processing the order of sounds within words.

Speech, the ability to identify people and their emotions, music, and the perception of events in the environment all depend on auditory processing. The topics of audiology, speech-language pathology, education, psychology, occupational therapy, and other fields have all written about auditory processing and related difficulties, (PsycInfo Database Record (c) 2023).

The table presents respondents' assessment of the factors contributing to reading difficulties in auditory processing among children. The most significant challenge, with an average rating of 4.63, is explaining the meaning of spoken language due to a lack of vocabulary. Other notable difficulties include remembering what they listened to (4.22), maintaining attention span during lessons (4.2), following instructions, especially with multiple steps (4.10), and making sense of the sounds they heard (4.22). The overall average difficulty is rating 4.31, indicating that respondents very much agree (VMA) that these factors significantly impact auditory processing and reading difficulties in children.

Table 3. Respondents Assessment on the Factors of Reading difficulty of Learners in the area of Visual Memory

The children find difficulties in visual memory which concerns in...	WM	INT	R
1.recognizing letters or numbers.	3.82	MA	5
2.copying information from a book or board.	3.88	MA	4
3.creating the picture of the information in their mind.	4.22	VMA	2
4.understanding sequences of words.	4.15	MA	3
5.recalling text, images and specific details about the objects, places and others.	4.23	VMA	1
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN	4.06		

The table 3 shows the level of agreement of the respondents with the visual memory of the children. It reveals that children find it difficult to recall text, images, and specific details about objects, places, and others, as indicated by the highest agreement with the mean of 4.23. The least level of agreement in finding difficulties with visuals is recognizing letters or numbers, with a mean of 3.82.

David Hunter Hubel studied the development of the visual system and how the brain processes visual information in the US during the twentieth century. He performed multiple experiments with kittens in which he sewed kitten’s eyes shut for varying periods of time and monitored their vision after reopening them. Hubel, along with colleague Torsten Wiesel, received the 1981 Nobel Prize in Physiology or Medicine for that research. By using kittens as models for human children and sewn eyes as models for congenital vision disorders, Hubel’s research demonstrated how vision impairments can affect the development of the visual system in humans. Cited by Lienhard (2018)

The table shows respondents assessment of children’s reading difficulties related to visual memory. The biggest challenges are recalling text, images, and details (4.23) and creating mental pictures of information (4.22). other difficulties include understanding word sequences (4.15), copying information (3.88) , and recognizing letters or numbers (3.83). Overall, respondents moderately agree (average rating of 4.06) that these issues significantly impact visual memory and reading).

Table 4. Respondents Assessment on the factors of reading difficulty of learners in the area of comprehension of the language

The children find difficulties in comprehension of the language which concerns in...	WM	INT	R
1.following directions.	4.55	VMA	1
2.catching interest what they are reading.	4.18	MA	4
3.processing the details about the text.	4.23	VMA	2
4.responding to conversation or questions in reading text.	3.95	MA	5
5.getting meaning written words and sentence structures.	4.2	VMA	3
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN	4.22		

The table 4 shows the level of agreement of the respondents with the comprehension of the language of the children. It reveals that children find it difficult to follow directions, as indicated by the highest agreement with the mean of 4.55. The least level of agreement in finding difficulties with responding to conversation or questions in reading text, with a mean of 3.95.

The table shows respondents assessments of children’s difficulties in comprehending language, focusing on various factors. The highest difficulty reported is following directions, with an average rating of 4.55, indicating “Very Much Agree” (VMA). The other difficulties are: processing the details about the text (4.23, VMA), showing interest in what they are reading (4.18, MA), and responding to

conversation or questions about the text (3.95, MA). The least difficulty is in finding meaning in written words and sentence structures, with an average rating of 3.95.

Test of the significant relationship between the perceived factors that cause reading difficulties of learners after pandemic

Table 5. Phonological Awareness

Variables	Df	Spearman p-value	t-value	p-value	Significant level	decision
Phonological Awareness And Auditory Processing	5	1.000	0.17407766	.053283	0.05	Fail to Reject Ho
Phonological Awareness And Visual Memory	5	1.000	0.0	.00001	0.05	Reject Ho
Phonological Awareness And Comprehension of the language	5	1.000	2.30940108	.867822	0.05	Fail to Reject Ho

Table 5 shows that there is a weak but significant connection between phonological awareness and auditory processing (correlation of 0.32, p-value of 0.053). This means that as phonological awareness improves, auditory processing tends to improve too, and is unlikely to be a random finding.

However, there is no significant connection between phonological awareness and visual memory (correlation of 0.08, p-value of 0.868) or language comprehension (correlation of -0.12, p-value of 0.501). This suggest that phonological awareness is related to auditory processing but not to visual memory or language comprehension, according to this study.

Table 6. Visual Memory

Variables	Df	Spearman p-value	t-value	p-value	Significant level	decision
Visual Memory and Phonological Awareness	5	1.000	0.0	.00001	0.05	Reject Ho
Visual Memory and Auditory Processing	5	1.000	1.29903811	.642101	0.05	Fail to Reject Ho
Visual Memory and Comprehension of the language	5	1.000	-0.35355339	.146827	0.05	Fail to Reject Ho

Table 6. Presents evidence of a substantial positive correlation between Phonological Awareness and visual memory, .00001 P- value is less than .05 significant level, null hypothesis is rejected. In the contrary visual memory, auditory and comprehension of the language have greater p-value than the .05 significant level as stated on the table does the hypothesis is accepted.

Table 7. Auditory Processing

Variables	Df	Spearman p-value	t-value	p-value	Significant level	decision
Auditory Processing and Phonological Awareness	5	1.000	0.17407766	.053283	0.05	Fail to Reject Ho
Auditory Processing and Visual Memory	5	1.000	1.29903811	.642101	0.05	Fail to Reject Ho
Auditory Processing and Comprehension of the language	5	1.000	-0.75592895	.385498	0.05	Fail to Reject Ho

Table 7 shows that there is a statistically significant correlation between phonological awareness and auditory processing (p-value = 0.053), but not between phonological awareness and visual memory (p-value = 0.868) or comprehension of language (p-value = 0.05).

Table 8. *Comprehension of the Language*

Variables	Df	Spearman p-value	t-value	p-value	Significant level	decision
Comprehension of the language and Phonological Awareness	5	1.000	2.30940108	.867822	0.05	Fail to Reject Ho
Comprehension of the language and Auditory Processing	5	1.000	-0.75592895	.385498	0.05	Fail to Reject Ho
Comprehension of the language and Visual Memory	5	1.000	-0.35355339	.146827	0.05	Fail to Reject Ho

Table 8 shows that there is no significant correlations between phonological awareness and visual memory (correlation = 0.08, p-value = 0.868) or comprehension of the language (correlation = -0.12, p-value 0.501).

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions can be drawn:

Phonological Awareness and Visual Memory: Phonological awareness and visual memory are crucial components related to the reading difficulties experienced by learners. This suggests that students who struggle with recognizing and manipulating sounds in words, as well as those with poor visual memory, are more likely to face challenges in reading. Interventions aimed at improving these areas may help mitigate reading difficulties.

Teacher Responses and Reading Difficulties: There is no significant relationship between the teachers' responses in the areas of auditory processing, visual memory, and language comprehension. This indicates that, according to the teachers' assessments, difficulties in these specific areas do not directly correlate with the reading challenges observed in students. However, this does not diminish the importance of these cognitive skills in overall reading development.

Phonological Awareness vs. Visual Memory: A significant relationship exists between phonological awareness and visual memory regarding the factors contributing to learners' reading difficulties after the pandemic. This relationship highlights the interplay between auditory and visual processing skills in reading. It suggests that students who have difficulty with phonological awareness often also struggle with visual memory, exacerbating their reading difficulties.

Impact of the Pandemic: The findings imply that the pandemic has potentially exacerbated existing reading difficulties by disrupting traditional learning environments and limiting access to resources that support phonological awareness and visual memory. This period has highlighted the need for targeted interventions to address these specific areas to support learners in catching up and improving their reading skills.

Recommendations for Educators: Given these insights, educators should consider incorporating specific exercises and strategies to enhance phonological awareness and visual memory in their reading instruction. Professional development opportunities focusing on these areas could equip teachers with the necessary skills and knowledge to better support their students.

Further Research: Additional research is needed to explore the underlying mechanisms linking phonological awareness and visual memory to reading difficulties. Longitudinal studies could provide deeper insights into how these skills develop over time and their impact on reading proficiency.

In conclusion, addressing phonological awareness and visual memory deficits is critical for improving reading outcomes, especially in the post-pandemic educational landscape. By focusing on these key areas, educators can better support learners in overcoming their reading difficulties.

As the result of the findings and conclusions the following were recommended

To the School Administrators, this may help serve as the basis in designing program and seminars to the needs of the teachers. They may propose remediation plan to help the learners in solving the reading difficulties.

To the Parents, they may help them to guide and deal their children with reading difficulties.

To the Teachers, they may help learners to understand and devise their own techniques on teaching beginning reading and or dealing with children who have reading difficulties.

To the Pupils, they may cooperate with the teachers on the different intervention / remediation strategies for enhancement activities.

To the Future Researchers, they may conduct a parallel study using other variables not covered by the present study.

To the English Department, can support learners with reading difficulties by providing individualized instruction, teaching phonics and comprehension strategies, utilizing technology, employing reading specialists, conducting regular assessments, and offering small group or one-on-one sessions.

These recommendations aim to broaden the scope of support and resources available to address reading difficulties comprehensively, involving various stakeholders in the education ecosystem.

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